

Effect of stacking sequence on the fracture toughness and fatigue delamination propagation behavior of composite laminates under mode I loading

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Abstract. Composite materials in the form of laminates consisting of continuous-fiber-reinforced plies are becoming widely applied in aerospace field. In such laminated structures, delamination is amongst the most usual failure modes, which generally originates from low velocity impacts and interlaminar stress raisers, e.g. free edges, ply drops, access holes, fabrication defects, etc. The delamination will further propagate and lead to considerable degradation of mechanical characteristics, even catastrophic failure of laminates, when the laminates are subjected to additional static loads or cyclic loads. Thus characterization of the fracture toughness and fatigue delamination resistance of composite materials is significant and essential for structural damage tolerant design and reliability assessment, which has attracted extensive investigation during past few decades. However, with regard to the multidirectional laminates, the studies are still limited due to the complication and some different phenomena such as fiber bridging, bifurcation, etc., which are evoked by the multi-directional stacked plies. Thus far there is not yet universal consensus on the effect of stacking sequence on the delamination behavior. To investigate the effect of stacking sequence on the fracture toughness and fatigue delamination propagation behaviors, static and fatigue experiments under pure mode I loading for unidirectional and multidirectional laminates made of T800 carbon/epoxy composites with various ply angle along mid-plane interfaces were carried out. The results indicated the fracture toughness of multidirectional laminates is higher than that of unidirectional one. Besides, the fracture toughness depends on the relative orientation of the adjacent plies along the mid-plane interface and the direction of delamination propagation relative to the fibers. With the increase of relative orientation of the adjacent plies, the effect of the direction of delamination propagation relative to the fibers on the fracture toughness will be smaller. Similar results can also be obtained in fatigue delamination growth. Furthermore,

accompanying with SEM images of the fracture surfaces after tests, the complex damage mechanisms, such as fiber bridging and bifurcation, etc. have been deeply investigated.

Reference:

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